

XS4900 Research Project for Sport and Exercise Sciences

**The effect of carbohydrate composition on gastric
fermentation and implications for interpretation of $^{13}\text{CO}_2$
breath test during exercise**

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to quantify the incidence and extent of carbohydrate maldigestion when consuming carbohydrate solutions at rates, and compositions, recently recommended to endurance athletes. Several recent studies have used ^{13}C tracer recovery in exhaled CO_2 to quantify exogenous carbohydrate oxidation during exercise. However, fermentation of carbohydrates by commensal bacteria in the gastrointestinal tract also produces CO_2 . The $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ breath test is often used to quantify carbohydrate malabsorption but is more specifically assessed by hydrogen and methane breath tests, since these products are produced by fermentation but not oxidation.

Six competitive racing cyclists cycled at 50% W_{Max} (maximum minute power) for 150 minutes whilst consuming either glucose or equimolar solutions of glucose and fructose, both delivering 1.8g of carbohydrate per minute. The incidence of carbohydrate maldigestion was assessed by clinical end tidal breath tests pre and post exercise. Using the generally accepted criteria of an increase in end tidal H_2 or CH_4 greater than 20 ppm or 15 ppm respectively, there was a 33% incidence of carbohydrate maldigestion in the glucose-fructose arm of the study. There was no evidence of maldigestion when participants consumed glucose. However, overall there was no significant difference in the mean post exercise breath H_2 or CH_4 concentrations between conditions.

Breath samples were collected every 15 minutes during exercise to assess the kinetics of breath H_2 and CH_4 production over exercise trials. Overall H_2 and CH_4 levels during exercise were very low, often below the limit of detection, however, the response was shown to be highly individual. Maximum individual values were recorded in the GF arm of the study, CH_4 , 6 ppm; max H_2 4 ppm. More sensitive analysis techniques are required in future studies in order to quantify the volume of H_2 and CH_4 produced during exercise. In this study there was no significant treatment or time effects on breath indicators of maldigestion during exercise.

This study adds to the understanding of CH₄ production in healthy participants. Two out of 6 participants were found to be significant CH₄ producers. One of the CH₄ producers produced a positive end tidal breath test suggesting that previous studies relying on H₂ measurements may have underestimated the incidence of maldigestion.

This is the first study to quantify the incidence of carbohydrate maldigestion with large fructose and glucose loads, comparable to those recently recommended to endurance athletes. A high incidence, and large individual variation was found in breath markers of gastric fermentation when participants consumed equimolar glucose and fructose solutions at high rates. The drinks in this study were generally well tolerated over the duration of the study. However, the positive breath tests suggest that some participants are likely to suffer gastrointestinal complications if they continued to consume glucose-fructose solutions at high rates for longer durations. This has implications for nutritional recommendations for endurance athletes, many of whom compete over much longer durations than 150 minutes.

It is recommended that future studies using sensitive ¹³CO₂ tracer recovery to quantify carbohydrate oxidation should account for potential bacterial CO₂ production. Simple clinical end tidal H₂ and CH₄ breath tests with commercially available equipment offer a simple solution to identify participants with significant maldigestion. More sensitive techniques are required to quantify the extent of carbohydrate fermentation during exercise.

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Abbreviations and definitions

ACSM – American College of Sports Medicine

bpm beats per minute

FODMAPs Fermentable Oligosaccharides, Disaccharides, Monosaccharides And Polyols

SFA – Short Chain Fatty Acids

PAR-Q Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (Csep.ca, 2015)

RER Respiratory exchange ratio ()

$\dot{V}O_{2Max}$ - maximum oxygen consumption in graded exercise test

W_{Max} - maximum minute power in graded exercised test.

$^{13}CO_2$ breath test – The measurement of carbohydrate oxidation through stable carbon isotope recovery in breath

Review of Literature

It is generally accepted that carbohydrate supplementation during exercise improves exercise performance. However, there is still much debate as to the optimum composition of substrates to maximize exercise performance. For many years it was thought that exogenous carbohydrate oxidation peaked at ~60g per hour and there was no benefit of supplementing carbohydrate beyond this level. The ACSM reflected this understanding in their position stand on nutrition and exercise performance recommending carbohydrate supplementation rates of 30-60g per hour of exercise (Rodriguez et al. 2009).

In recent years several researchers have demonstrated much higher exogenous carbohydrate oxidation rates with the co-administration of high doses of glucose and fructose (Jentjens et al., 2004a; Jentjens, 2004b; Jeukendrup et al., 2005). The leading research groups in this area have campaigned for the guidelines to be updated to reflect the findings of their work (Jeukendrup, 2014; Jeukendrup 2010).

The high exogenous carbohydrate oxidation rates demonstrated by this group involved the consumption of significant quantities of fructose. Jentjens and Jeukendrup (2005) gave equimolar doses of glucose and fructose at an average rate of 144g per hour, to demonstrate peak exogenous oxidation rates of 105g per hour.

Interest in high dose fructose supplementation to improve exercise performance has been paralleled by intense scrutiny concerning the adverse health consequences of fructose consumption. Fructose has been linked to cardiovascular disease, hypertension, diabetes, cancer, uric acid production and non-alcoholic liver disease (Johnson et al., 2010; White, 2013).

Lustig (2013) suggested that consuming over 50g of fructose per day is toxic, whilst in a paper largely defending fructose, White (2013) conceded that fructose can cause adverse metabolic effects when consumed either in doses much higher than normal daily amounts, or in a ratio to glucose greater than 1:5. In perspective, participants in Jentjens and Jeukendrup (2005) study consumed 95g of fructose in the first hour and a

total of 180g over a 2.5-hour period; more than 3 times the daily toxic dose suggested by Lustig.

In a short exercise model Fernández and colleagues (2009) showed that when fructose was given with glucose prior to a post-prandial exercise session, oxidative stress was induced which was not evident when only glucose was given. This study suggests that exercise, or consuming high doses of fructose during exercise may not offer any protection against the potential adverse effects of fructose consumption.

There may therefore be negative long-term consequences of consuming high levels of fructose in carbohydrate supplements. Further, although most exercise studies suggest that drinks with a high fructose to glucose ratio are better tolerated than pure glucose drinks, fructose intolerance is a common problem (Beyer et al., 2005).

Critically, an assumption made by all the studies reporting enhanced exogenous carbohydrate oxidation with high co-consumption rates of glucose and fructose is that ^{13}C tracer recovery in exhaled breath reflects exogenous carbohydrate oxidation in muscle. However, fermentation of sugars by commensal bacteria in the gastrointestinal tract also produce CO_2 , so it is possible that increased tracer recovery in exhaled breath is due to increased bacterial fermentation rather than oxidation by muscles. For this reason, Corpe and colleagues (1999) concluded that the $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ breath test is of limited value for measuring fructose absorption. Highlighting that it is not possible to differentiate between oxidation and fermentation over time, and both contribute to $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ excretion in breath.

Several review papers do however describe a facilitative effect of glucose on fructose absorption, suggesting that malabsorption is ameliorated if fructose consumption is matched with equal or greater quantities of glucose (Jones, Butler and Brooks, 2010; DiNicolantonio and Lucan, 2015; Latulippe and Skoog, 2011). The absence of malabsorption would remove bacterial production of CO_2 as an error in the measurement of carbohydrate oxidation through ^{13}C tracer recovery. It would also remove the possibility of non-digested fructose causing osmotic effects in the lower gastrointestinal tract.

However, the primary research used to substantiate the facilitative effect of glucose on fructose absorption is limited to relatively low fructose loads, see table 1. There is one recent single blind, randomised study, with 16 participants showing no evidence of maldigestion when 40g of fructose was consumed with 40g of glucose (Murray et al., 2013). The two studies that studied doses as high as 50g both recorded some evidence of maldigestion at this level (Rumessen and Gudmand-Hoyer, 1986; Kneepkens, Vonk and Fernandes, 1984). Whilst Rumessen and Gudmand-Hoyer (1986) reported symptoms of maldigestion without an increase in breath hydrogen, Kneepkens, Vonk and Fernandes (1984) reported an increase in breath hydrogen of 5 ppm (range 0 -19 ppm) in comparison with 103 ppm (range 34-250 ppm) with 50g of fructose only. It is clear that co-administration glucose with fructose does facilitate fructose absorption however; the facilitative effect appears to diminish with increasing fructose loads.

None of the studies measured breath methane to account for fermentation by methanogenic bacteria, there are no double blind studies, and no studies at levels greater than 50g of fructose. Importantly, there are no studies reported in the literature that have investigated the maldigestion of comparable fructose loads to those used in recent exercise studies (Jentjens et al., 2003; Jentjens, 2004; Jentjens and Jeukendrup, 2005) at rest or during exercise.

High fructose loads are more likely to result in fermentation since fructose empties from the stomach faster than other sugars, and the capacity for absorbing fructose in the small intestine can easily be exceeded (Beyer, 2005). Further, exercise has been shown to accelerate gastric emptying of fructose, increasing the chances of undigested fructose reaching colonic bacteria (Fujisawa, 1993).

Colonic fermentation, or maldigestion is routinely diagnosed by the hydrogen breath test which is more specific to fermentation since hydrogen is not produced when carbohydrate is oxidized by muscles. Researchers have used combined hydrogen and ¹³C breath tests to distinguish between oxidation and fermentation of resistant starch (Symonds et al., 2004; Wang et al., 2008).

Positive hydrogen breath tests have been reported after the consumption of sports drinks and glucose-fructose solutions during exercise at far more modest fructose loads

than those used in the recent multiple energy substrates studies (Fujisawa et al., 1993; Mitsui et al., 2001). Peters et al. (1993) similarly reported positive hydrogen breath tests during exercise and linked carbohydrate malabsorption to the incidence of gastrointestinal cramps and urge to defecate.

There is a high incidence of fructose malabsorption associated with gastrointestinal distress in normal adults. In a recent study two thirds of participants receiving a single 50g dose showed evidence of maldigestion (Beyer, Caviar and McCallum, 2005). Further, the researchers in this study suggested that the real incidence might be higher since they measured breath hydrogen but not methane. Similar to hydrogen, methane is produced from fermentation of sugars by methanogenic microorganisms in the gastrointestinal tract where it is absorbed into the systemic circulation and excreted unchanged by the lungs. Breath methane could therefore be another source of tracer recovery in exhaled breath (de Lacy Costello, Ledochowski and Ratcliffe, 2013).

The maintenance of some colonic fermentation during exercise may convey some potential performance benefits. In a recent study gastric fermentation of an evening barley starch meal was shown to increase peripheral tissue uptake of glucose on the following morning. Colonic fermentation was confirmed by hydrogen breath test and associated with an increase in butyrate levels, it was thought that this contributed to improved glucose uptake into tissues (Priebe et al., 2009). Butyrate may also improve the uptake of fluids and electrolytes, and improve mitochondrial function via stimulation of the peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (Canani, 2011).

The composition and consumption rate of carbohydrate supplementation during exercise is likely to have implications on the rate and type of fermentation end products. High carbohydrate loads that empty more quickly from the stomach are less likely to cause upper gastrointestinal discomfort. However, more rapidly transported carbohydrates are more likely to reach bacteria in the lower gastrointestinal track undigested.